

VIRTUAL RESEARCH ENVIRONMENT AS A FACTOR IN THE PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF A MODERN SCIENTIST IN THE CONTEXT OF ENVIRONMENTAL UNCERTAINTY

Oleksii Vernik

Candidate of Psychological Sciences,
Leading Researcher
G.S. Kostiuk Institute of Psychology of
the National Academy of
Educational Sciences of Ukraine,
Kyiv, Ukraine
avernik@meta.ua

Yuliia Vernik

Researcher Fellow,
Department of Biobibliographic
Information Resources Formation,
Institute of Biographical Research,
Vernadsky National Library of Ukraine,
Kyiv, Ukraine
vrnkjl@gmail.com

The concept of “virtual research environment” (VRE) entered the scientific and organizational lexicon at the beginning of the twenty-first century and means a system of automated workplaces for researchers. The idea of considering the set of professional workplaces of researchers as an integral system was innovative for at least two reasons.

First, it was perhaps the first time in the management and organization of scientific activities that attention was focused not on administrative or general issues of labor organization, but on the effectiveness of communication between researchers in the process of implementing research projects. This means, first of all, the development of platforms that will ensure the sustainability of research projects and facilitate the involvement of various specialists in them. This is not just another technological solution, but an effective tool for forming virtual scientific communities, often multidisciplinary, united around at least one scientific problem. Collaboration tools, specialized tools for data analysis, visualization, simulation management, document storage and exchange are becoming an essential component of such platforms. Between 2004 and 2011, JISC funded the creation of several such platforms under the Virtual Research Environment program and established the VRE knowledge base in 2011, which became a catalog of international projects and key research in this area [1].

Secondly, the researcher's "workplace" itself becomes a concept in which there is a rejection of traditional ideas about professional activity as a specific place associated primarily with physical territory, premises, furniture, devices, etc., that is, everything that in classical engineering psychology and ergonomics was considered as "PM" in the system of functioning "operator - machine". The workplace of a scientist becomes an integral element of the environment of his or her professional activity. Moreover, the environment is beginning to be understood in the context of environmentalism - as a basis that determines not only the current behavior of a person, but also his or her development and formation throughout life. Therefore, the environment approach provides for the possibility of technologizing the process of indirect management of personal development, including professional development.

The virtual research environment is characterized by [2]:

- accessibility to data, tools and resources;
- interaction and collaboration with other researchers;
- independence of such cooperation from institutional or geographical affiliation;
- access to Big Data, both input and results of individual studies.

The issue of the professional development of a national scientist is especially relevant in the context of prolonged uncertainty caused by social changes that have been taking place over the past 4 years not only in the world due to the pandemic and forced social isolation, but also, and above all, in Ukraine in the context of war. Current social and economic conditions are far from conducive to a positive solution to this problem. A modern graduate of a Ukrainian university, when choosing a further professional path, faces significant problems in the prospects for further scientific growth, including underfunding of domestic science, obsolete equipment in research institutes, extremely low wages, etc.

In such circumstances, virtual research environments are becoming almost the only factor in the further professional development of young researchers, as it is through VRE that the idea of building modern scientific communities is being affirmed. As part of this development, it is envisaged [1]:

- openness of research projects for the creation of international interdisciplinary communities;
- remote access to modern computing resources and research tools, including supercomputers and quantum computing;
- providing researchers with training opportunities to improve their professional competencies, including skills in working with new tools;
- involvement of researchers themselves in formulating requirements and evaluating implementation, which requires constant feedback and flexibility, etc.

List of references:

1. Carusi, Annamaria & Reimer, Torsten. (2010). Virtual Research Environment Collaborative Landscape Study. JISC Report.

2. Assante, M.; Candela, L.; Castelli, D.; Cirillo, R.; Coro, G.; Dell'Amico, A.; Frosini, L.; Lelii, L.; Mangiacrapa, F.; Pagano, P.; Panichi, G.; Piccioli, T.; Sinibaldi, F. (2022). Virtual research environments co-creation: The D4Science experience. *Concurrency Computat Pract Exper.* doi:10.1002/cpe.6925